

Bromination of 2-Hydroxyacetophenones and Preparation of Some Benzofurylchromones*

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Bromination of 2-hydroxyacetophenones has been studied. 2-Hydroxyacetophenone and 4-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone on bromination with equivalent amount of bromine in glacial acetic acid, give mixture of the ω -bromo and nuclear brominated compounds. The ω -bromo compounds were separated through pyridinium salts and the nuclear brominated compounds were isolated from mother liquors. The orientation of the bromine atom in 5-bromo-4-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone was confirmed by NMR study. 3-Bromo-5-methyl, 3-bromo-5-chloro- and 5-bromo-3-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenones were similarly prepared. The esters obtained by esterification of the hydroxyacetophenones with coumarilic acid, on Baker-Venkataraman transformation gave diketones, which on cyclisation yielded the chromones, the structures of which were confirmed by i. r. spectra.

WE required several ω -bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenones in connection with some other work and bromination of the corresponding 2-hydroxyacetophenones appeared to be the most obvious route. Buu-Hoi *et al*¹ have studied the bromination of 4-hydroxyacetophenone and 4-hydroxypropiofenone. They observed that while bromination of such compounds with bromine in acetic acid medium produced mainly the ω -bromo-compounds (which were highly lachrymatory), bromination in aqueous acetic acid medium resulted in nuclear bromination. The nuclear brominated compounds (reported to be produced in "substantial amounts") were invariably the dibromo compounds, even when equimolecular amounts of the ketone and bromine were used. These authors could not obtain mononuclear brominated compounds.

When 2-hydroxyacetophenone was brominated in glacial acetic acid using equimolar proportion of bromine, an oily product resulted which was somewhat lachrymatory. Although, 5-bromo- and 3 : 5-dibromo-2-hydroxyacetophenones are both solids^{2,3}, all attempts to obtain crystalline material from the above oil failed. Treatment of the oil with excess anhydrous warm pyridine afforded the crystalline pyridinium salt of the ω -bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone (cf.4). The pyridine filtrate on working up, gave an oil which soon solidified, and this on recrystallisation furnished 5-bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone. This procedure thus resulted in a

new route to 5-bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone which on similar bromination gave the crystalline 3 : 5-dibromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone. From the above observations the bromo-compounds obtained from 5-methyl-, 5-chloro- and 3-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenones have been assigned as 5-methyl-3-bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone, 5-chloro-3-bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone and 3-methyl-5-bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone respectively.

Bromination of 4-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone also gave a mixture of nuclear and side chain brominated products. The side chain brominated compound was removed as the pyridinium salt, and the structure of the purified nuclear brominated product was established as 5-bromo-4-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone from its NMR spectrum which showed two sharp singlets for the two aromatic protons at δ 7.09 and δ 8.08. All the bromo-compounds discussed above gave the benzoyl-derivatives and oximes by the usual procedure. These bromo-compounds were individually condensed with the acid chloride of benzofuran-2-carboxylic acid by heating a mixture of the two⁴. The same products were obtained by condensing the bromo-compound and the acid itself in anhydrous pyridine using phosphorus oxychloride as the condensing agent⁵. The yields by the latter process were in each case better than the former (*vide* experimental). The benzofuran-2-carboxylic esters I(a-f) thus obtained were converted into 1 : 3-

I_a, II_a, III_a=R₁=R₂=H; R₃=Br.
I_b, II_b, III_b=R₂=H; R₁=R₃=Br.
I_c, II_c, III_c=R₂=H; R₁=Br; R₃=Cl.
I_d, II_d, III_d=R₂=H; R₁=Br; R₃=CH₃.
I_e, II_e, III_e=R₂=H; R₁=CH₃; R₃=Br.
I_f, II_f, III_f=R₁=H; R₂=CH₃; R₃=Br.

* After communication of this paper an earlier work (Buu-Hoi *et al* *J.C.S.* 1955, 18) regarding bromination of 2-hydroxyacetophenone and its 5-methyl derivative has come to our notice.

propanediones II_(a-r) by Baker-Venkataraman transformation in dioxan. Cyclodehydration of these 1:3-propanediones in acetic acid containing catalytic amount of conc. hydrochloric acid afforded the substituted chromones III_(a-r).

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The i. r. spectra were recorded in Beckman infrared spectrometer Model DK-2A.

5-Bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone and ω-bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone pyridinium salt (Preparation and separation from a mixture of the two acetophenones) :

To a solution of 2-hydroxyacetophenone (1.36 g) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was added with stirring a solution of bromine in acetic acid (1.6 g/8 ml) at room temperature and stirring was continued till the colour due to bromine disappeared. The solution on dilution with water gave an oil which failed to give any crystalline material. The oil was extracted with benzene and the benzene layer was successively washed with water, 2% sodium carbonate solution, water again and dried (MgSO₄). Removal of benzene gave an oil (moderately lachrymatory) which was dissolved in dry pyridine (6 ml) and kept at 60° for 40 mins. The crystals which separated were filtered out and repeatedly washed with small quantities of anhydrous pyridine. The solid *1-(2'-hydroxyphenacyl) pyridinium bromide*, (cream coloured) melted at 224-25°, yield 0.25 g. Its aqueous solution gave a positive test for bromide ion and developed a green colour with ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 52.9, H, 3.5; C₁₁H₁₂O₂NBr requires C, 53.1, H, 4.1%).

The pyridine filtrate was poured with stirring into an excess of hydrochloric acid (1:1) containing crushed ice. A solid mixed with viscous oily material separated. This on treatment with ethanol yielded crystals (0.3 g) which on recrystallisation from aqueous ethanol melted at 61-62° (lit.⁸ 62°). The melting point was not depressed on admixture with an authentic sample of 5-bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone, *oxime*, m.p. 172-73°, benzoyl derivative, m.p. 129-30° (aq. methanol).

3:5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone was similarly prepared using 5-bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone (1.5 g), acetic acid (30 ml), bromine (0.37 ml) in glacial acetic acid (8 ml). Yield 1.6 g; not lachrymatory, cream coloured needles (ethanol), m.p. 109-110° (Lit.⁸ 110°; *oxime*, m.p. 202-03 (Lit.⁸ 203°), benzoyl derivative 83-84° (aq. ethanol).

The following compounds were similarly obtained. Their names, appearance, yield, m.p., solvent of crystallisation are given below :

5-Chloro-3-bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone. cream coloured needles, 65%, m.p. 104-05°, ethanol (Found :

C, 38.3, H, 2.3; C₈H₆O₂BrCl requires C, 38.5, H, 2.4%); *oxime* (aq. methanol) m.p. 200-01°, *benzoyl derivative* (aq. methanol) m.p. 118-19°.

5-Methyl-3-bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone. cream coloured needles, 65% mp. 94-95°, ethanol (Found : C, 47.6, H, 3.8; C₉H₉BrO₂ requires C, 47.1, H, 3.9%), *oxime* (aq. ethanol) m.p. 204-05°, *benzoyl derivative* (methanol) mp. 110-11°.

3-Methyl-5-bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone : cream coloured needles, 66%, 77-78°, ethanol (Found : C, 47.5, H, 3.8%), *oxime*, (aq. methanol) m.p. 150-52°, benzoyl derivative (aq. methanol) m.p. 79-80° (appreciable depression on admixture with parent compound m.p. 77-78°).

4-Methyl-5-bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone and 1-(2'-hydroxy-4'-methyl phenacyl) pyridinium bromide :

4-Methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone (4 g) on similar bromination gave an oil (lachrymatory) which similarly gave the above pyridinium bromide, yield 0.25 g as colourless needles m.p. 235-36° (Found : C, 54.2, H, 4.6; C₁₁H₁₄O₂NBr requires C, 54.5, H, 4.5%). The pyridine filtrate similarly afforded *4-methyl-4-bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone* (1.5 g) as wooly needles, m.p. 86° (methanol). (Found : C, 47.0, H, 3.7; C₉H₉BrO₂ requires C, 47.2, H, 3.9%); *oxime* (aq. ethanol) m.p. 124-25°.

2-(2'-Benzofuroxy) acetophenones :

Method (i) : The bromohydroxyacetophenone (0.02 mole) and benzofuran-2-carboxylic acid (0.025 mole) were dissolved in dry pyridine (15 ml) and phosphorus oxychloride (1.4 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring, keeping the temperature below 60° by surrounding with ice cold water. After stirring at room temperature for a further two hrs the mixture was treated with ice cold hydrochloric acid (1:1). The solid product was washed successively with water, sodium carbonate solution (10%), sodium hydroxide (1%) water and then recrystallised from ethanol. The names, percentage yield, mps. and appearance of solids are given below :

I_a *5-Bromo-2-(2'-benzofuroxy)acetophenone* (65%) 154-55°, colourless.

I_b *3:5-Dibromo-2-(2'-benzofuroxy)acetophenone* (91%), 137-38°, cream.

I_c *3-Bromo-5-chloro-2-(2'-benzofuroxy)acetophenone* (96%), 155-56°, cream.

I_d *3-Bromo-5-methyl-2-(2'-benzofuroxy)acetophenone* (50%), 159-60°, cream.

I_e *3-Methyl-5-bromo-2-(2'-benzofuroxy)acetophenone* (90%), 119-20°, cream.

I, 4-Methyl-5-bromo-2-(2'-benzofuroxy)acetophenone, gummy mass.

Method (ii): A mixture of the bromohydroxyacetophenone (0.002 mole) and the chloride from benzofuran-2-carboxylic acid (0.002 mole) was heated in a hard glass test-tube in an oil bath at 170-80° for 4 hrs. The contents were extracted with benzene, and the benzene solution was washed successively with water, sodium hydroxide (2%) and water. Benzene was removed and the product was recrystallised. Yields: Ia-63%, Ib-10%, Ic-14%, Id-47%, Ie-15%, If-20%. Melting points were not depressed on admixture with corresponding samples obtained by method (i).

2-Hydroxy- ω -(2'-benzofuroyl)acetophenones II_(a-1): The benzofuroxyacetophenone (0.001 mole) was dissolved in anhydrous dioxan (8 ml) and treated with powdered potassium hydroxide (0.001 mole). The mixture was gently refluxed for 30 mins. with exclusion of moisture. The mixture was cooled and acidified with dil. sulphuric acid. An oily mass was initially produced which solidified after a few minutes. The solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised. The names, yields, m.ps. solvents of crystallisation and colours are given below:

IIa 5-Bromo-2-hydroxy- ω -(2'-benzofuroyl)acetophenone (65%), 61-62° (Lit⁷. 159-60°), ethanol, deep yellow. (Found: C, 56.6, H, 3.0, C₁₇H₁₁O₄Br requires C, 56.8, H, 3.1%)

IIb 3 : 5-Dibromo-2-hydroxy- ω -(2'-benzofuroyl)acetophenone (84%), 191-92°, ethanol and benzene, yellow.

(Found: C, 46.1, H, 2.9, C₁₇H₁₀O₄Br₂ requires C, 46.6, H, 2.3%)

IIc 3-Bromo-5-chloro-2-hydroxy- ω -(2'-benzofuroyl)acetophenone (88%), 180°, ethanol and benzene, deep yellow.

(Found: C, 51.6, H, 2.5, C₁₇H₁₀O₄BrCl requires C, 51.8, H, 2.5%)

IId 3-Bromo-5-methyl-2-hydroxy- ω -(2'-benzofuroyl)acetophenone (84%), 172-73°, ethanol, deep yellow.

(Found: C, 58.3, H, 3.6, C₁₈H₁₃O₄Br requires C, 57.9, H, 3.5%)

IIe 5-Bromo-3-methyl-2-hydroxy- ω -(2'-benzofuroyl)acetophenone (90%), 167-68°, ethanol, deep yellow. (Found: C, 58.0, H, 3.5%)

IIIf 5-Bromo-4-methyl-2-hydroxy- ω -(2'-benzofuroyl)acetophenone (74%), 179-81°, ethanol, deep yellow. (Found: C, 57.9, H, 3.8%)

All the products II_(a-1), were soluble in caustic alkali and gave positive ferric test.

2-(2'-Benzofuroyl) chromones III_(a-1):

To a solution of a 2-hydroxy- ω -(2'-benzofuroyl)acetophenone (0.001 mole) in glacial acetic acid (6 ml) was added one drop of conc. hydrochloric acid and the mixture was refluxed for 30 mins. It was cooled and diluted with ice cold water. A gummy mass produced initially soon solidified. The solid was triturated with sodium hydroxide solution (2%), filtered, washed thoroughly with water and recrystallised from ethanol. The names, yields in %, mps. and colours are noted below:

IIIa 6-Bromo-2-(2'-benzofuroyl)chromone⁷ (90%), 239-40°, brownish white.

IIIb 6 : 8-Dibromo-2-(2'-benzofuroyl)chromone, (98%), 213-14°, light yellow. (Found: C, 48.1, H, 2.2; C₁₇H₈O₃Br₂ requires C, 48.5, H, 1.9%)
KBr_{max} ν 1660, 1640, 1560 cm⁻¹.

IIIc 8-Bromo-6-chloro-2-(2'-benzofuroyl)chromone (98%), 197-98°, greenish yellow.

Found: C, 54.1, H, 2.9, C₁₇H₈O₃BrCl requires C, 54.3, H, 2.1% KBr_{max} ν 1650, 1635, 1560 cm⁻¹.

IIId 8-Bromo-6-methyl-2-(2'-benzofuroyl)chromone (95%), 253-54°, colourless.

Found: C, 60.3, H, 3.4; C₁₈H₁₁O₃Br requires C, 60.8, H, 3.1% KBr_{max} ν 1660, 1640, 1565 cm⁻¹.

IIIe 6-Bromo-8-methyl-2-(2'-benzofuroyl)chromone (96%), 195-96°, colourless.

(Found: C, 60.6, H, 3.5%)

KBr_{max} ν 1665, 1605, 1560 cm⁻¹.

IIIIf 6-Bromo-7-methyl-2-(2'-benzofuroyl)chromone (90%), 219-21° light brown.

(Found: C, 60.4, H, 3.2%)

KBr_{max} ν 1660, 1610 cm⁻¹ and this agrees with the expected data⁽⁷⁻⁹⁾.

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